

AN INNOVATIVE TOOL FOR DESIGNING FAULT TOLERANT COCKPIT DISPLAY SYMBOLOGY

James A. Uphaus, Jr.
Cockpit Integration Division
Wright Laboratory
Wright-Patterson AFB, Ohio 45433-7511

Capt Richard Barry Bryant
Dayton Detachment
ASC Reserve Program
Wright-Patterson AFB, Ohio 45433-7511

ABSTRACT

This research focuses on the design and development of a software package to aid display designers in creating fault tolerant fonts and symbology for monochrome dot-matrix displays. Since dot-matrix displays are subject to non-catastrophic failures [rows, columns, and individual picture elements], display designers find it necessary to address hardware reliability as a key design element when avoidance of operator reading errors is mission critical. This paper addresses row and column failure modes. Building redundancy into the design of font characters and symbology can provide additional protection from reading errors. The software package developed for the design of fault tolerant fonts, referred to herein as FontTool, operates on an IBM PC or compatible hardware platform within a Microsoft DOS environment. FontTool can simulate row or column dot-matrix display failures and "predict" likely human reading errors. Based on limited testing, FontTool reading error "predictions" were found to be consistent with actual human performance reading error data about 86% of the time. FontTool uses Euclidean distance between 2-D Fourier transformed representations of dot-matrix characters as a metric for predicting character "similarity". Although this metric has been applied previously, FontTool is a major advance in aiding display designers to build more fault tolerant cockpit display symbology.

INTRODUCTION

The design of fonts and symbology for military aircraft displays takes on an additional level of complexity when the display device to be used is based on dot-matrix as opposed to Cathode Ray Tube (CRT) technology. The potential for non-catastrophic failures [rows, columns, and individual pixels (picture elements)] is one source of this additional complexity. Occurrence of these failure modes is a concern when such failures can lead to crew members misreading displayed information. Although steps may be taken to minimize the probability of such failures from a hardware reliability perspective, incorporating redundancy into the design of fonts and symbology can provide an additional measure of protection from reading errors.

The focus of this research is the development of a tool, hereafter referred to as FontTool, to facilitate the design of fault tolerant dot-matrix fonts and symbology for monochrome cockpit displays. This tool will aid the designer in identifying characters and symbols which have a high potential for being misread when degraded by display failures.

Dot-matrix display devices may exhibit the following types of failures: discrete pixels may fail in either the **OFF** or **ON** state, and rows or columns of pixels may fail either **ON** or **OFF**. Failures in the **ON** state are of less concern because these provide a continuous warning to the operator that the display contains defects which must be compensated for. Failures in the **OFF** state can only be detected by the absence of pixels known to be part of a normal character or symbol. The effects of discrete pixel failures have been investigated by Bush [1], Pastor [2], Uphaus [3], and Riley and Barbato [4]. Tannas has addressed failures in segmented displays [5,6]. The effects of single row or column failures for a 7x9 dot-matrix symbology set were investigated by Uphaus, Reising, and Barthelemy [7].

Row/column failures can lead to one of three outcomes: fail redundant (the operator correctly reads the character), fail safe (the operator identifies the character as not readable), and fail error (the operator identifies the degraded character as another character) [3].

DESIGNING THE TOOL

Background

Previous studies have relied on the use of Euclidean distance between 2-D Fourier transform data as a metric for assessing the similarity between characters within a font [1,3]. The correlation between Euclidean distance and perceived similarity between characters has varied depending upon experimental conditions. Tests performed to date have not provided sufficiently convincing evidence in the opinion of the authors to warrant high reliance on this metric as a single source of modeling the similarity between characters within a font. However, this metric was chosen by the authors as the "best" known starting point for development of the font design tool.

The font illustrated in Figure 1 was selected for use in developing a tool which helps identify single row or column failures that are most likely to cause reading errors of the "fail error type". Figure 2 shows versions of the characters in Figure 1 that were degraded by a group of human subjects [7]. The subjects participating in the process of degrading these characters followed two rules. Rule 1: fail a single row or column in a character in Figure 1 to make the degraded character look most like another undegraded character in the font. Rule 2: if it was not readily apparent how to degrade one character to make it look like another, then fail a single row or column to make a degraded character which is most unlike any other character in Figure 1.

A symbol or character can be completely described by its Fourier components, however FontTool limits the data used by low-pass filtering the Fourier data. The Fourier coefficients are used to generate a one dimensional array with N components, where N is a function of the square of the filter order.

FontTool "transforms" a symbol from the "pixel bit" data to the spatial frequency domain. The transform data is stored in a one dimensional array containing the magnitudes of the real and imaginary terms of the 2-D Fourier transformed pixel data. The transform arrays are treated as vectors in an N dimensional space. The vector's direction in the N dimensional space is a function of the spatial

Figure 1. Undegraded Test Font

Figure 2. Test Font Degraded by Human Subjects

Theory

FontTool uses the 2-D Fourier transform to analyze symbol data. Typically, the Fourier transform is used to analyze a function of time, in which case it generates a function in cycles per second or Hertz. FontTool operates on symbol data which is stored as a two dimensional array of bits representing the pixels of a symbol. An ON pixel is represented as a one bit and an OFF pixel is represented as a zero bit. Accordingly, arrays resulting from Fourier transforms of symbols or characters contain data that is a spatial frequency representation of the character pixel (bit) position data.

characteristics of the symbol. The vector's magnitude is a function of the symbol's energy, or the number of ON pixels. In order to limit the comparisons of the Fourier data to comparisons of the spatial characteristics of the symbols, the transform data vectors are normalized to a length of one unit. Thus, each character within a font would be described by a unique vector, and the collection of all vectors in this N dimensional space would represent the font. Within this space, vectors which represent two symbols are compared by calculating the distance between the ends of the symbol vectors. Since the symbol vectors are normalized to a length of one, the distance between two symbol vectors will range from 0.0 for identical symbols to 2.0 for symbols which are

FontTool. FontTool automatically assigns a .XFM extension to each symbol file which is transformed using 2-D Fourier transform techniques. Using the default extensions, the transform file of the file "L." would be "L.XFM". A transform file consist of the original symbol data appended with the normalized Fourier coefficients generated from a two dimensional Fourier transform of the symbol data. Since the original symbol data is saved in the transform data file, the transform data files can be opened and displayed in the FontTool GUI environment.

Matrix Data files are generated by calculating the Euclidean distance between sets of transform data files. The matrices are generated from two sets of transform data files. These sets are described as DOS paths within FontTool's options file. Figure 5 shows a matrix data file generated by comparing a set of two transform files to another set of two transform files. The file includes header information which describes symbol set paths and transform parameters. As in transform data files, the symbol data for all of the symbols involved is appended to the end of the matrix data file. Note that the appended symbol source data and some of the header information has been removed for this example. The resulting matrix is a two by two matrix of Euclidean distances. In this example, a set consisting of an 'F' and an 'I' is compared with a set consisting of an 'O' and a 'P'. From an inspection of the array, you can see that the 'F' and 'P' have the closest Euclidean distance. This example has very small sets and a small matrix data file. For any two sets of sizes N and M, the resulting matrix file has NxM Euclidean distance elements.

```

Transform Filter Order> 3
Distance Order> 2
Begin MATRIX Data
      F.XFM I.XFM
O.XFM 1.2973 1.2978
P.XFM 0.5378 1.4603
End MATRIX Data

```

Figure 5. Example Matrix Data File

Sort Data files are generated by reformatting the information in the matrix data files. A sort data file contains a list of elements. Each element contains a symbol name from each set and the Euclidean distance between the two elements. Finally, as the name implies, the elements are sorted based on the Euclidean distances. Again, the sort file has header information about the symbol sets and transform parameters as well as appended symbol data. The symbol data and header information have been removed from the example shown in Figure 6. Within the FontTool GUI, the sort file data is displayed within a display as shown in Figure 3 and Figure 7. This display shows columns of symbols with the Euclidean distance displayed numerically between the two symbols of a column. If the sort file contains more symbol pairs than can be displayed at once, as

in Figure 7, the display has arrows which allow the user to scroll through the pairs of symbols in the sort file.

```

Begin Sort Data
Set 1 Files  Set 2 Files  Distance Value
F.XFM      P.XFM      0.5378
F.XFM      O.XFM      1.2973
I.XFM      O.XFM      1.2978
I.XFM      P.XFM      1.4603
End Sort Data

```

Figure 6. Example Sort Data File

Option Files contain operating parameters for the FontTool program. When FontTool executes, if no option file exists, FontTool will create an option file with default options. This file can be edited with a text editor to create custom configurations. The new option file is then saved under a unique name. Significant parameters kept in the option file include SET 1 and SET 2 path information, default file extensions, transform filter order, distance calculation order, and the pixel dimensions of new symbols.

Directory Structure

FontTool is designed to operate on sets of symbol data and transform data files. The sets are defined by describing a DOS path for each set and then file name extensions for each type of file analyzed. Transform data files can be created by transforming individual files within a directory so that only a subset of the symbol data files have corresponding transform data files, or by transforming all symbol data files in any directory. FontTool places transformed files (*.XFM) within the same working directory as their respective symbol files.

FontTool maintains two set paths, SET 1 and SET 2. Matrix data files are generated by comparing all of the transform data files in the SET 1 path to all of the transform data files in the SET 2 path.

FontTool also maintains an analysis data path to the matrix and sort data files. If an analysis path is specified, the matrix and sort data files are stored in that path with their respective extensions. If no analysis data path is specified, the matrix and sort data files are stored in the directory with the FontTool executable.

FontTool Modules

Upon execution from DOS or within MS Windows, FontTool displays a full screen work environment with the following module functions displayed across the top: **File**, **Options**, **Analysis**, **Tools**, and **Quit**. Program status is displayed in the top right corner. The label **Ready** is displayed whenever the program is capable of accepting operator input. Kilobytes of **Available Memory** are displayed in the lower right corner, to give the operator a feel

for the memory used while generating distance matrix files. The **Current Symbol Path** is displayed in the lower left corner of the work environment whenever its symbol matrix is displayed in the "active window". An active window is denoted by a black shadow below and to the right of the window, a double line border around the box, and a small box with an "x" in it in the upper left corner of the window. A non active window may be made active by placing the cursor anywhere within the non active window and clicking the left mouse button. The operator's mouse and keyboard inputs only have control over the active window.

Symbol Editor

The symbol editor is used to turn pixels off and on within the symbol matrix contained in the active window. OFF pixels are displayed in white and ON pixels in black. OFF pixels are turned ON by using the mouse to place the cursor over the pixel to be turned ON and clicking the left mouse button. Clicking the left mouse button on an ON pixel turns this pixel OFF.

Clicking the right mouse button anywhere within the active symbol window displays a sub menu of additional editing functions. These functions are: **Reverse, Clear, Shift Up, Shift Down, Shift Left, Shift Right, Stretch Up, Stretch Down, Stretch Left, Stretch Right, and Exit Menu.**

File

Clicking the left mouse button when the cursor is over the **File** label displays a file menu with the following options: **Open File, New, Save, Save As, Save All, Undo, Exit.** Open, Save, Save As and Save All allow the user to edit and save existing symbol files. Undo allows the user to undo any changes that have been made to a symbol since the last time the symbol was saved.

New symbols can be created by opening a template symbol, modifying it and using Save As to save the modified symbol with a new name. The File menu's **New** command is also used to create a new symbol file. The size of the matrix displayed for editing a new symbol is specified in the options file (FontTool.opt). The size limits on the symbol matrix imposed by FontTool are 50x50.

Options

The option menu item, allows the user to control the configuration of FontTool's options. The option menu provides **Load Configuration, Show Configuration and Default Configuration** options. Load Configuration allows the user to load an option file. Once the new option file is loaded, the options contained in that file take effect immediately. Show Configuration shows the options currently in effect. Default Configuration switches all options back to their default values. These controls provide user configurability for different data sets, transform parameters and symbol sizes.

Analysis

The following functions are executable provided that a symbol file is currently open:

- **XFM Current Symbol** -- This function accomplishes a 2-D Transform on the symbol currently displayed in the active window.

- **XFM Current Directory** -- This function transforms all symbols within the directory containing the symbol in the active window.

- **Degrade Current Symbol** -- FontTool has the capability to generate degraded symbols from any symbol data. That is, the data may contain any font style or newly created symbol that fits within the symbol matrix. This function degrades the symbol in the active window N+M ways, computes the 2-D transform of each resulting symbol and stores the resulting .XFM file in a sub directory called degrade. The currently implemented method of degradation is to clear N rows (one row at a time) and M columns (one column at a time), thereby resulting in N+M .XFM files. Other degradation methods are planned as future options for FontTool's **Degrade** function.

Once the degrade operation is selected, the tool looks for a "DEGRADE" directory below the directory of the current symbol. For example if the symbol data file is in the path "C:\DATA\MYFONT", FontTool will look for the directory "C:\DATA\MYFONT\DEGRADE". If that directory does not exist, FontTool will create it. Once the directory is created, if necessary, FontTool will: (1) degrade the active symbol, (2) calculate the transform data for the degraded symbol, and (3) write the transform to the "DEGRADE" directory. This procedure can be repeated for as many of the symbols data files as desired, generating more degraded symbol files in the "DEGRADE" directory with each degrade

Each .XFM file containing a degraded version of the active symbol is assigned a unique file name by FontTool. The first character of the file name corresponds to the file name of the active symbol being degraded..

- **Generate Matrix** -- This function generates a matrix with column labels that correspond to the names of all the SET 1 files and row labels corresponding to all of the SET 2 file names (see Figure 5). Each matrix cell contains a value corresponding to the Euclidean distance between the symbols identified by the respective row and column names. The matrix file is assigned the generic file name MATRIX.DAT and is stored in the same directory with FontTool.exe.

- **Show Sort Data** -- Selection of the this function causes the contents of the MATRIX.SRT file to be graphically displayed. Figure 7 shows the Sort Data Results for degrading an "E". Note that the degraded "E" was closest to an undegraded "F" when FontTool uses Euclidean distance as the metric for sorting. This degradation is consistent with the human operator's degradation of an "E" as shown in Figure 2. FontTool's "prediction" that the degraded "E"

would be identified as an "F" is also validated by the fact that 21 out of 22 human subjects called this "E" an "F" in the previous study [7].

been created, the *.XFM files can be deleted to clear the way for other sets of *.XFM files.

Figure 7. FontTool Analysis / Sort Example

Analysis Sort has the flexibility to be used in a number of ways. This sort can be accomplished by changing the contents of the files whose paths are specified by SET 1 and SET 2. For example, a symbol set can be compared with itself to look for similarity between symbols within the set. This can be accomplished by placing all .XFM files for a symbol set in the "lowest" sub directory of the SET 1 and SET 2 paths. Alternatively, a symbol set may be compared with a different set or multiple versions of a degraded symbol. This comparison is accomplished by placing all .XFM files of the former in the lowest sub directory of the SET 1 path and all .XFM files of the latter in the lowest sub directory of the SET 2 path.

Tools

FontTool provides a tool option which includes some file maintenance utilities. These allow the user to delete all of the *.XFM files within the current SET 1 or SET 2 paths. These options are helpful when looking at subsets of the symbols contained in a directory. Once the matrix and sort files have

Quit

Quit terminates FontTool execution, closes all active and inactive windows, and returns control to the MS DOS prompt. Quit will ask for confirmation before exiting. FontTool can also be exited via the **Exit** option under the **File** menu which does not ask for confirmation.

TESTING AND DEVELOPMENT OF FONTTOOL

Objective

The objective in test and development of FontTool was to design a software based model which fails a single row or column of a character the same way human subjects did when applying Rule 1 (see **Background**, Figure 2). This model was optimized by changing filter order and distance order (in the Fourier transform domain) to produce degraded characters that most often match degraded characters created by human operators.

Initial Tool Development

Utilizing data collected in a previous study [7], testing was performed for this study to ascertain the correlation between Euclidean distance and character identifications. Various levels of filter order and distance order (straight line or "taxi") were applied to build matrices of Euclidean distance values for the undegraded and degraded fonts shown in Figures 1 and 2. These matrices were then restructured to form data records, each record consisting of a character pair followed by 8 different Euclidean distance values. Each Euclidean distance value corresponded to a unique filter order/distance order combination. An example of three data records is shown in Figure 8.

CPR	ID	DST1	DTX1	DST3	DTX3	DST5	DTX5	DST6	DST7
COW	22	.335	.857	.685	3.586	.792	6.747	.797	.705
JUW	22	.233	.607	.294	1.771	.327	3.238	.326	.317
FEW	21	.276	.707	.268	1.683	.301	2.985	.326	.225
DBW	3	.457	1.086	.596	3.297	.694	6.107	.661	.531
EE	22	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

Figure 8. Euclidean Distance, Error Data Records

Column 1 shows character pairs. The first entry "COW" is interpreted as follows: "O" is displayed to the human subject, "W" indicates that the "O" was degraded worst case, and "C" is the response given by 22 subjects participating in the test. "ID" corresponds to the number of subjects calling the degraded "O" a "C". In this case the identifications were errors. The remaining columns contain Euclidean distance data. In the column headings "D" implies Euclidean distance, "ST" connotes straight line, "TX" - taxi, and 1, 3, 5, 7, etc. correspond to filter order. The last data record corresponds to showing an undegraded "E" in the test. All 22 subjects participating in the test called this undegraded "E" an "E". The Euclidean distance between an undegraded "E" and itself was zero regardless of the filter order or distance method.

The resulting data records were then loaded into SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) and correlation tests were performed. A filter order of 5 coupled with use of the straight line distance method produced a Euclidean distance array with the highest correlation to the character identification data collected in the previous study. The corresponding Pearson correlation coefficient was -0.658.

Metrics and Methods

Euclidean distance was used as the metric by the FontTool **Analysis Sort** function for identifying and sorting font characters previously degraded with the **Analysis Degrade** function. To facilitate tool development, a subset of the previous study data [7] was selected for testing. This subset consisted of "human" degraded characters that exhibited 10 or more errors by human test subjects. The

corresponding error rate was 45% [10/22] since 22 subjects participated in the previous study [7]. Two combinations of filter/distance order were evaluated: [filter order-1, distance-straight] and [filter order-5, distance-straight].

Data records were constructed using the following input data: character pair identification ["human" degraded character, test subject identification (most frequent) of this character], filter/distance order, FontTool predicted character identifications and corresponding Euclidean distance values. If the FontTool **Analysis Sort** function predicted matches between the degraded character and its undegraded version, these matches were discarded. For example, if FontTool **Analysis Degrade** produced 3 different degraded versions of a "Q" and FontTool **Analysis Sort** predicted that these degraded "Q"s would be identified as undegraded "Q"s, then these predictions would be discarded. It should be noted that FontTool has an **Analysis Sort** sub function, **Omit Derived Matches**, which the operator may use to accomplish this. If FontTool predicted matches between more than one degraded version of the same character degraded by **Analysis Sort** and an undegraded character, only one instance per unique undegraded character was placed in the data record. This instance corresponded to the degraded/undegraded character pair with the lowest Euclidean distance. For example, if FontTool "predicts" that 3 different versions of the letter "O" would be identified as a "Q", then only the degraded "O" closest in Euclidean distance to a Q was placed in the data record. Each unique undegraded character followed by its distance to the degraded character formed by **Analysis Degrade** was added to the data record until a match was achieved between the FontTool created degradation and the "human" created degradation in the previous study [7]. Thus, data records created in this manner would contain unequal numbers of elements. An example of three data records is shown in Figure 9.

[(O, C), 5, Straight]: (Q, 0.591), (U, 0.569), (0, 0.663), (D, 0.736), (G, 0.775), (C, 0.792)
[(U, J), 5, Straight]: (J, 0.327)
[(G, C), 5, Straight]: (C, 0.768)

Figure 9. Three Data Record Samples.

An index value was then assigned to each data record based on the total number of unique character identifications sorted by **Analysis Sort** until a match was achieved between the **Analysis Degrade** created character and the "human" created degraded character in Figure 2. For example, the index values of the three data records in Figure 7 would be 6, 1, and 1 respectively. Accordingly, the lower the index value, the more rapid **Analysis Sort** converges on a match to "human" created character degradation.

Mean and Standard Deviation (S.D.) were computed for the index values corresponding to the eight degraded

characters exhibiting the highest human subject misread rates in a previous study [7]. These misread rates ranged from 45% to 100% with a mean of 76.2% and a S.D. of 24.3%.

The mean index for the filter order-5/degradation-straight combination was 5.1 with a corresponding S.D. of 7.4. The mean index for the filter order-1/degradation-straight combination was 2.0 with a corresponding S.D. of 1.1. Based on these results the filter order-1/degradation-straight combination was selected for further test and analysis.

Using the FontTool **Analysis Degrade** and **Sort** functions, each character in Figure 1 was degraded and sorted until a match was achieved between the "human" degraded character in Figure 2 and the **Analysis Sort** character identified by FontTool. The corresponding undegraded character identified by **Analysis Sort** as closest in Euclidean distance to the "human" degraded character was recorded. Using this data, a set of thirty-six data records was constructed for further statistical testing. Each of these records contained the following data: (1) the "human" degraded character, the FontTool identified character which is closest in Euclidean distance to the human degraded character, the computed Euclidean distance between these characters, and the total number of human test subjects matched the prediction by **Analysis Sort**. The data records were subdivided into two sets for statistical testing. The first set of data records [Group 1] corresponds to degraded characters that were correctly identified by human test subjects. The second set [Group 2] corresponds to degraded characters that were incorrectly identified (reading errors).

Test Results

Group 1: Based on human performance data collected in the previous study [7], 11 or more subjects (out of a total of 22 subjects) correctly identified 20 of the degraded characters in Figure 2. FontTool Sort was used to "predict" which undegraded character would be identified when each degraded character in Figure 2 was compared with all other undegraded characters in Figure 1. FontTool Sort predicted that 14 of these degraded characters would be correctly identified. Thus, FontTool's predictions were consistent with human performance about 58% of the time.

Group 2: If 11 or more subjects incorrectly identified a degraded character in Figure 2 and all 11 subjects' responses were in agreement, then each response was placed in a data record. FontTool's character predictions of these errors were consistent with the errors recorded in the data records 86% of the time.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

FontTool's capability to degrade font characters and "predict" reading errors was consistent with error data obtained using human subjects about 86% of the time. Other combinations of filter order and distance order, as well as algorithms for sorting Euclidean distance data remain to be

examined. The authors currently plan to continue researching these parameters as well as other metrics to further enhance the utility of FontTool.

REFERENCES

1. Bush, L. F., "The Design of an Optimum Alphanumeric Symbol Set for Cockpit Displays", 1977, Thesis, Master of Science, Air Force Institute of Technology.
2. Pastor, J. R., Uphaus, J. A., Jr., "Significant Reading Errors in 7x9 Dot-Matrix ASCII Numbers with Two-Percent Dot Loss", *Society for Information Display, SID 1982 Digest*.
3. Uphaus, J. A., Jr., Pastor, J. R., "Investigating the Correlation Between Reading Errors and Degraded Numerics: Or, Do Missing Dots Call the Shots?", *NAECON 82 Proceedings*, p. 734-738.
4. Riley, T. M., Barbato, G. J., "Dot-Matrix Alphanumerics Viewed Under Discrete Element Degradation", *Human Factors*, 1978, p. 473-480.
5. Tannas, L. E., Jr., "Fail safe Matrix Fonts", *Society for Information Display, SID 1977 Digest*, p. 54-55.
6. Tannas, L. E., Jr., *Flat Panel Displays and CRTs*, Van Nostrand Reinhold Co., 1985, p. 7-9.
7. Uphaus, J. A., Jr., Barthelemy K. K., Reising, J. M., "Improve Character Readability in Spite of Pixel Failures, A Better Font", *NAECON 90 Proceedings*, p.278-283.